

Photoactivity Enhancement by Electrochemical Activation of Bifunctional V₂C@S MXene: Desirable Approach in Single-architecture High-rate Zinc-ion Solar Batteries

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Abstract. Single-architecture solar battery energy storage devices which are capable of storing energy from solar energy harvesting in only one package, are being developed as the upcoming and future off-grid energy storage systems. In this research, we explore the photo-responsive characteristics and application of vanadium-based MXene in pouch zinc-ion solar batteries. In addition to the pristine V₂CT_x MXene, a sulfur-incorporated nanocomposite of V₂CT_x@S was synthesized via a reaction between exfoliated V₂CT_x MXene and sulfur at a high benign temperature to evaluate the efficiency of both as photocathodes for such state-of-the-art devices. Through the initial electrochemical charging activation, photoactivity of the V₂CT_x@S photocathode was enhanced significantly because of the formation of nanoscale vanadium oxide on the surface of conductive V₂CT_x MXene and the presence of sulfur element without losing the MXene nanolayered characteristics. The results of the pouch zinc-ion solar battery made by V₂CT_x@S indicate a specific capacity of 197 mAh g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ under illumination, compared to the dark condition with the amount of 114 mAh g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ (72.8% enhancement). Additionally, the V₂CT_x@S zinc-ion solar battery carried out a photo-charging voltage response of 700 mV, and a remarkable energy density of 255 Wh kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ under illumination compared to dark conditions with the energy density of 150 Wh kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹. Furthermore, a photoconversion efficiency of ≈2.04% was obtained in the pouch zinc-ion solar battery. Density functional theory studies supported these experimental findings by revealing that sulfur modification and vanadium oxide formation improve the electronic properties and light

absorption capabilities of the pristine V_2C MXene, contributing to its superior photocathodic performance. These great achievements in photo-electrochemical behaviors of $V_2CT_x@S$ are due to the catalytic synergy of bifunctional MXene decorated with sulfur element, the formation of outer high-valence vanadium oxide, and inner conductive of V_2CT_x . The findings provide crucial insights into designing of highly efficient photocathode materials for advanced solar batteries.

1. Introduction

Growing worldwide anxieties over the depletion of natural fuels, escalating carbon emissions, and their role in climate change have driven the advancement and importance of renewable energy sources and sustainable technologies for storing energy.^[1] Among various types of sustainable energy storage systems, solar batteries and solar capacitors stand out as a pioneering category of devices that aim to seamlessly incorporate energy harvesting capabilities within energy storage systems.^[2] The current technologies typically rely on discrete charging components, such as photovoltaic and battery units connected via DC-DC converters or stacks.^[3] Nevertheless, there is growing interest in the integration of photovoltaic and battery cells into a single setup as a two-in-one concept. This approach provides several fascinating advantages such as simpler implementation, better energy matching between each component, enhanced flexibility, decreased ohmic transport loss between individual components, lowered production expenses, and smaller packaging size.^[4] Consequently, these categories of devices have garnered increasing interest recently and are becoming significant, particularly in off-grid energy storage, and Internet of Things equipment.^[5] Furthermore, progress in equipment and materials designed to find the demands of the energy storage and conversion segments has further boosted their relevance and potential impact.^[2a, 6]

Integrated solar battery or solar capacitor devices can be classified into two main configurations: (i) three-electrode setups, consisting of a photovoltaic electrode, cathode and anode, and (ii) two-electrode setups, which utilize either bifunctional cathode and anode or bifunctional anode and cathode.^[4b] Three-electrode structures have been explored by photoelectrodes within batteries,^[7] or through various solar redox flow battery designs.^[8] On the other hand, two-electrode configurations are enabled by either applying layers of photoactive materials onto the battery or capacitor's anode through the process of deposition,^[9] or by creating composites (i.e., as photocathode) that combine charge storage materials with photoactive materials.^[10] Recent research efforts have shown that the third approach is gaining momentum particularly if it is designed as a single-architecture, where bifunctional

photoelectrochemical storage materials can absorb light and store charge within a single architecture. Most attempts focus on expanding novel photocathodes to improve the performance of solar energy storage and minimize energy loss during transmission between separate sections. The mechanism behind these dual-functional materials typically includes two key steps of generating photoexcited electrons through solar energy absorption, followed by a direct transport of these photogenerated electrons into the storage system.

Among the various classified materials with different elements and structures, vanadium-based materials have garnered significant attention to be used in both of conventional,^[11] and new solar batteries.^[12] This is due to the diverse compositions, crystal structures, and suitable band gap values of such materials, as well as their great discharge capacity (i.e., 589 mAh g⁻¹ for V₂O₅), which originates from the multi-electron redox reactions of vanadium.^[13] However, most vanadium-based electrodes, particularly those including vanadium oxides, suffer from low electronic and ionic conductivities, characteristics necessary for energy storage devices, thus limiting their ability to efficiently store metal ions at high rates. To enhance battery performance, two fundamental approaches are essential: (i) developing novel materials with large electronic and ionic diffusion, and (ii) reducing the characteristic dimensions of the electrode. Therefore, designing vanadium-based cathodes/photocathodes possessing a high level of diffusion, especially at nanoscale dimensions, is crucial for achieving high energy density, rapid charging, and large capacitance enhancement under illumination.

With the emergence of V₂CT_x MXene, known for its exceptional conductivity and valuable surface chemistry,^[14] a significant opportunity for developing high-performance solar batteries has emerged. The unique accordion-like structure of V₂CT_x, which consists of numerous stacked V-C-V monolayers, features well-organized nanochannels that enhance charge transport. These nanochannels can function as a circuit with multiple branches running in parallel, thereby delivering high power output.^[15] Moreover, the V₂CT_x structure offers ample surface area, providing sufficient active sites for the intercalation and deintercalation of metal ions in a battery system. Despite these advantages, there have been few reports in using V₂CT_x as a cathode material for traditional batteries and none for solar batteries, primarily due to its unexpectedly low discharge capacity and photoactivity. Recent investigations have indicated that the poor redox activity of V₂CT_x MXene is primarily referred to the low valence states of its vanadium atoms (V⁺² and V⁺³), which are unable to engage in multi-electron redox reactions during charge and discharge cycles.^[14, 15c] Given the typical multi-electron transfer capability of vanadium, it is possible to achieve high and rapid metal ion storage capabilities, enhance the storage capacity, and raise the photoactivity of V₂CT_x. This can be done by elevating the

valence state of vanadium atoms and performing surface nanoscale modification using specific elements, all while preserving the conductivity and nanolayered shape of the V-C-V configuration.

In this study, we report our pioneering approach to fabricate a bifunctional $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene-based photoactive cathode and utilize it in a pouch zinc-ion solar battery, while also exploring the charge transfer mechanism of such a device. We were also inspired by a recent in-situ electrochemical activation technique discovered by Liu *et al.*,^[15c] to explore its impact on the photoactivity of $V_2CT_x@S$, where the mechanisms are unclear or have yet to be studied. Through initial electrochemical charging activation, the photoactivity of the $V_2CT_x@S$ photocathode was greatly improved by the formation of a nanoscale vanadium oxide layer on the surface of the conductive V_2CT_x MXene, coupled with the chemisorbed/substituted sulfur atoms, all while maintaining the MXene's nanolayered structure. The results from the pouch zinc-ion solar battery using $V_2CT_x@S$ demonstrated a specific capacity of 197 mAh g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ under illumination, compared to 114 mAh g⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ in the dark. Furthermore, the pouch zinc-ion solar battery achieved a photo-charging voltage response of 700 mV and an impressive energy density of 255 Wh kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ under illuminated conditions, compared to 150 Wh kg⁻¹ at 1 A g⁻¹ in the dark.

2. Experimental procedures

2.1. Sample preparation

2.1.1. Synthesis of pristine V_2CT_x MXene

The pristine V_2CT_x MXene was synthesized using the standard method with as-received V_2AlC MAX material (supplied by Jinzhou Haixin Metal Materials, China), hydrofluoric acid (HF) solution (50% vol, Sigma-Aldrich), hydrochloric acid (HCl) solution, lithium fluoride (LiF), and distilled water.^[16] Firstly, 40 g of the V_2AlC MAX material was stirred in 600 mL of HF solution for two days under ambient conditions. The blend was centrifuged regularly, diluted with distilled water, and poured off repeatedly to attain a neutral pH value in the solution. Next, the wet product obtained from the previous stage was combined with 400 mL of HCl, 40 g of LiF, and 100 mL of distilled water. It was allowed to mix at room temperature for three days before being diluted with 2 L of distilled water and poured off several times. Following that, a blend of 400 mL of 50% HF and 300 mL of 35% HCl was added to the wet product and agitated for several additional days, then diluted with 2 L of distilled water and poured off multiple times. The final product was mixed with 400 ml of distilled water and 200 mL of tetramethylammonium hydroxide (25% vol) and stirred for four days. Further, the solution was

diluted with 2 L of distilled water and poured off. The most recent powder was mixed with 500 mL of distilled water, shaken for a few minutes, and centrifuged frequently until having a neutral pH, before freeze-drying the final product and placing it in the argon-filled glovebox.

2.1.2. Synthesis of $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene

The $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene was synthesized by combining 1 g of pristine V_2CT_x MXene from the previous step with 0.281 g of as-received sulfur powder (99.99%, Strem chemicals, USA). These two components were thoroughly blended and placed into a quartz tube, which was then sealed under a vacuum ($\approx 10^{-5}$ mbar) by an oxygen-hydrogen torch.^[5b, 17] Subsequently, the sealed quartz tube was inserted in a muffle furnace, where the mixed sample was annealed for 24 hours at 500 °C with temperature control (heating and cooling) rates of 5 °C min⁻¹. After the annealing process, the quartz tube was broken, and the product was collected and stored in argon-filled glovebox.

2.1.3. Preparation of V_2CT_x MXene-based photocathodes

160 mg of each synthesized V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXenes were thoroughly mixed with 20 mg carbon black (99%) to create pathways for charge carriers, and 20 mg polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF, Thermo Fisher Scientific) as binder in 2 mL of N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP, 99%, Acros Organics, Thermo Fisher Scientific) solvent. The suspension was sonicated for about 30 minutes and then stirred continuously at 400 rpm for 24 hours to obtain a homogeneous slurry before drop-casting onto the appropriate substrate.

2.2. Characterization methods

2.2.1. Materials characterization

The phase identification and crystal structure of the pristine V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXenes were characterized using the X-ray diffraction (XRD) technique at room temperature by Bruker D8 Discoverer (Bruker, Germany) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406$ Å, $I = 40$ mA, $U = 40$ kV). The samples were placed on a silicon plate with zero diffraction, and the data were scanned across the angular spectrum from $2\theta = 5$ to 90° and a step size of 0.02° . Raman spectroscopy (Renishaw, England) was conducted on each sample using backscattering geometry connected with a CCD detector to determine the structure of phases. The MXenes were mounted on a metal plate as a powder and evaluated instantly after the deposition. The Raman characterizations were measured by a DPSS green laser with 532 nm wavelength an exposure time of 1 s in incident power (5 mW), 128 accumulations, and an objective lens of 20 \times . The

silicon peak position (520 cm^{-1}) was used as a reference for calibrating the Raman device prior to the measurement. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to investigate the surface composition of the V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{SMXenes}$, utilizing a SPECS spectrometer with a monochromatic Al K_α X-ray source (1486.7 eV) and a Phoibos 150 hemispherical electron analyzer. The survey spectra were obtained using E_p set at 100 eV, while the high-resolution spectra of the core lines were recorded using E_p set at 40 eV. The base chamber pressure within the acquisitions was $< 10^{-9}$ mbar. Due to a heavy charge development on the samples' surface, a low-energy electron flow generated by an electron flood gun has been used to compensate for the charge buildup. The morphology and distribution of elements in the MXene samples and photocathode electrodes (pre- and post-cycling stabilities) were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy included with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM/EDS, Tescan Lyra 3) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with a JEOL 2200 FS and JEOL monochromated ARM200F microscopes at 200 kV.

In order to achieve detailed spatial instruction about localized electrochemical reactivity at the microscale level, scanning electrochemical microscopy (SECM, Sensolytics, Germany) was utilized as appropriate analytical equipment. This method allows for mapping the physical properties of the surface materials, charge transfer kinetics, and catalytic activity. The feedback mode of SECM was employed to map the surface conductivity of V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXene-based electrodes. During performing a four-dimensional (4D) array scan, an ultramicroelectrode (UME) moves towards the surface from the bulk solution on top of the particular area of the sample and remarks variations in the Faraday current. These changes can be affected by factors like sample reactivity, surface roughness, distance between the electrode and the surface, UME size, and geometry of the diffusion region around it. In this study, a Pt UME working electrode tip with a $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ diameter was used to scan the surface of the electrodes over a selected area of $100\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$, with $2.5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ increments in both X and Y directions. A Pt wire with a spiral shape served as a counter electrode. SECM analysis was performed in a potassium ferrocyanide redox system solution with 10 mmol L^{-1} ferrocyanide $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ and 0.1 mol L^{-1} potassium chloride (KCl) as a redox mediator and support electrolyte, respectively. The potential of UME was adjusted to 0.5 V relative to the Ag/AgCl reference electrode to facilitate the redox reaction $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-} \rightarrow \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-} + e^-$ and establish a steady state condition. The MXene-based slurries were drop-casted on the silicon wafer and placed in the SECM measurement cell. Bulk current (i_{bulk}) was taken at the height of $1000\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ above the surface of the measured sample. Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) technique was also used to survey the specific surface area of the V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXenes. N_2 adsorption isotherms were

conducted at 77 K using a NOVAtouch series (Quantachrome Instruments, Anton Paar QuantaTec Inc., USA) to determine the BET area and characterize the materials' pore size distribution. Prior to measurements, all samples were activated at 120 °C for 15 h under a vacuum (38 torr).

2.2.2. *Electrochemical characterization*

The photoactivity and electrochemical behaviors of the pouch zinc-ion solar battery were analyzed under dark and illuminated conditions using Autolab PGSTAT 204 (NOVA, Utrecht, Netherlands) potentiostat. A variety of techniques like chronoamperometry, cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) were utilized for analysis at this stage. The CV and GCD data were measured at diverse scan rates, ranging from 1 to 10 mV s⁻¹, and specific currents from 1000 to 20,000 mA g⁻¹, both at the voltage window of 0.2–1.5 V. EIS measurements were taken using an open circuit potential at a voltage amplitude of 10 mV and the frequency range of 100 mHz to 100 kHz, in both dark and illuminated settings. Chronoamperometry tests were also conducted at 0, 0.2, and 1.5 applied voltages by an LED source of 435 nm wavelength under 35 mW cm⁻² light intensity to evaluate the photocurrent activity of each sample. Furthermore, a three-electrode setup was used to analyze the photocurrent responsivity of the samples by the same potentiostat machine. To do so, 10 µl drop-casted V₂CT_x and V₂CT_x@S MXene-based samples on PET-coated ITO/Au substrates were used as working electrode, platinum (Pt) wire as a counter electrode, and Hg(l)/Hg₂Cl₂(s)/KCl(sat) as a reference electrode. In this three-electrode system, the photocurrent activity of the MXene samples was examined at zero applied voltage under illumination with 435 nm, 533 nm, and 630 nm wavelength LED sources, and light intensity of 35 mW cm⁻² and 75 mW cm⁻² using chronoamperometry characterization.

2.2.3. *Density functional theory calculations*

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were carried out by Synopsys Atomistix Toolkit. In order to optimize the geometric structures, the generalized gradient approximation (GGA) with the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) functional was chosen to represent the exchange-correlation potential.^[18] The GGA-PBE function is well-regarded for its effective balance between computational efficiency and accuracy in characterizing the electronic properties of materials. Given the importance of accurately describing long-range van der Waals (vdW) interactions, the Grimme DFT-D3 vdW correction with DJ Damping approach was included in all calculations.^[19] This correction is essential for systems where dispersion forces play a

significant role in the stability and structure of the materials. The valence electron configurations for the atoms involved in the calculations were explicitly considered to ensure accurate electronic structure representations. The specific valence electron configurations included: vanadium: $3p^6 3d^4 4s^1$, carbon: $2s^2 2p^2$, oxygen: $2s^2 2p^4$, and sulfur: $3s^2 3p^4$. All geometric structures were fully relaxed using stringent convergence criteria. The iterative solution of the Kohn-Sham equations continued until the energy change and forces on all atoms were less than 1×10^{-4} eV and $0.01 \text{ eV}\text{\AA}^{-1}$, respectively, ensuring that the structure is fully relaxed. The Monkhorst-Pack scheme was employed for the sampling of the Brillouin zone. $6 \times 6 \times 1$ k-point mesh, with a k-point spacing of 0.3636 \AA^{-1} , was used for the supercell calculations.^[20] This optimal k-point sampling ensures accurate integration over the Brillouin zone, which is essential for reliable electronic structure calculations. To prevent spurious interactions between periodic images due to the use of periodic boundary conditions, a vacuum layer of 15 \AA was introduced. This separation is sufficient to ensure that the calculated properties are intrinsic to the material under study and not influenced by image interactions. Based on the literature, we first determined the most optimal crystal structure for the synthesized MXene as a V_2C monolayer. The V_2C monolayer is made up of ternary layers with atoms stacked V-C-V. The optimal lattice parameters for a V_2C monolayer are $a = b = 2.88 \text{ \AA}$, with V-C bond lengths of 2.05 \AA . It is obvious that the lattice parameters are completely inline with prior theoretical calculations and experimental results.^[21] In the oxygen and sulfur functionalized V_2C after geometric calculations, all groups tend to be situated on vanadium sites (as the most stable configuration), in agreement with experimental results and previous studies.^[21c] Further V_2CO_2 layers were functionalized with sulfur in three different positions V_2CO_2 -S (sulfur is adsorbed at the surface site), V_2CO -S1 (oxygen atom got substituted with sulfur alternatively), and V_2CO -S2 (oxygen atom got substituted with sulfur opposite) monolayer as shown in **Figure S1**.

3. Results and discussion

The crystal phases, surface chemistry, structure, and morphology of the synthesized V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXenes were thoroughly characterized using XRD, Raman spectroscopy, XPS, SEM, and TEM/HRTEM techniques. The XRD and Raman results confirm that after etching of the V_2AlC MAX phase with HF, well-crystallized V_2CT_x MXene is formed with some remaining Al element (**Figures 1a,b**). In general, the critical heating temperature for the MXenes chemical and structural phase transitions is known to be approximately $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.^[22] Therefore, an annealing temperature of $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was chosen to modify the surface chemistry of

V_2CT_x MXene with sulfur element without compromising the MXene structure. The XRD pattern and Raman spectra of $V_2CT_x@S$ revealed that upon sulfur decoration, some typical MXene peaks disappeared, replaced by some additional sharp diffraction peaks corresponding to newly formed phases of V_2C-O-S and V_2C-S (**Figures 1a,b**). These transformations occurred due to a reaction between sulfur atoms and the MXene layers, resulting in a possible formation of covalent bonds.

This substitution process involved the elimination of $-OH$ and some $-F$ surface functional groups, which created vacancies that were filled by sulfur atoms.^[23] XPS was employed to further investigate the surface chemistry, chemical states, and bonding configurations of the synthesized V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXenes (**Figures 1c-g**). High-resolution XPS spectra revealed an increase in oxygen content and the disappearance of V-C bonding after sulfur decoration. This was attributed to the substitution of surface functional groups during annealing, oxygen-containing terminations such as $OC=O$, C-O, and a high doping rate of sulfur. Usually, three potential anchoring sites for sulfur atoms on V_2CT_x MXene could be identified including (i) bonding with terminal groups to form S-O species, (ii) bonding directly with surface vanadium atoms, and (iii) occupying vanadium vacancies created during the etching process.^[23-24] This is supported by the formed V_2C-O-S and V_2C-S surface layers and chemical bonding between sulfur with oxygen, vanadium, or possible vanadium vacancies. SEM, TEM, HRTEM, EDS, and electron diffraction images of V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXenes acknowledge the nanolayered structure of the V_2CT_x MXene including a trace of $-F$, $-O$, and Al, as well as its structural stability after decoration with the sulfur agent under vacuum annealing (**Figures 1h,i** and **Figure S2**). These findings were consistent with XRD results and demonstrated that the V_2CT_x MXene retained its few-layered structure while gaining new chemical species on the surface due to the sulfur incorporation.

In the next step, localized electrochemical reactivity of the V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene-based slurries were investigated by SECM device. The top view 2D and 3D topographical mappings of current distribution near the surface of both drop-casted samples in two normalized and common current conditions are presented in **Figures 2a-f** and **Figures S3a-f**, respectively. The mappings in **Figures 2a-f** provide a detailed visualization of the normalized tip current (i_{norm}) values along a scanned line. The i_{norm} values were calculated by normalizing the measured current in the bulk electrolyte (i_{bulk}) far from the surface, where the current reaches a steady state. This normalization allows for a direct comparison of the electrochemical performance of the samples under SECM investigation. In SECM feedback mode, the measured current is

influenced by both surface roughness and physical properties, such as the geometry and conductivity of the samples.

Figure 1. (a) XRD patterns, (b) Raman spectra, (c-g) High-resolution XPS spectra, (h) SEM, and (i) TEM, HRTEM images and electron diffraction patterns of the synthesized V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene nanopowders.

Figure 2. (a, d) 2D and (b, e) 3D topographical mapping of catalytic activities of drop-casted V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene-based slurries, along with the normalized tip current (i_{norm}) and roughness (z) values of the (c) V_2CT_x and (f) $V_2CT_x@S$ corresponding to the 2D topographical results.

When UME is getting close to an insulating (non-electroactive) surface, the diffusion of the redox mediator is obstructed, leading to a current suppression. Conversely, when the UME is close to an electrochemical active or conductive surface, the current enhances despite the obstructed diffusion layer, because the mediator is being regenerated on the surface.^[10b, 25] As shown in **Figures 2c,f**, the current peak at $x = 45 \mu\text{m}$ indicates that the contribution of roughness to the overall measured current is minimal. Further, the magnitude of the peak is greater than i_{bulk} . Hence, the positive feedback current observed between 40 and 70 μm on the x-axis in the $V_2CT_x@S$ sample can be possibly attributed to its higher conductive properties. Moreover, the i_{norm} value of the $V_2CT_x@S$ sample shows higher electroactivity than the pristine V_2CT_x sample. This enhancement is attributed to the superior regeneration of the $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-} + e^- \rightarrow \text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ redox reaction on the $V_2CT_x@S$ sample surface, which is facilitated by its better conductivity and/or higher electrochemical activity. The superior performance of $V_2CT_x@S$ sample is likely due to the additional S atoms and formation of new chemisorbed or intercalated species modifying its composition, which effectively enhances its electrical properties compared to the pristine V_2CT_x sample. These elements contribute to faster electron transfer processes, thereby improving the overall conductivity and electrochemical performance of the $V_2CT_x@S$ material. The step-by-step preparation process of the pouch zinc-ion solar battery is illustrated in **Figure 3**. Initially, a flexible substrate with a rectangular shape ($2 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$) made of polyethylene terephthalate coated with indium tin oxide ($\approx 80 \text{ nm}$) and gold ($\approx 20 \text{ nm}$) (PET-coated ITO/Au) was chosen for the photocathode side (**Figure 3a**). The selected PET-coated ITO/Au was covered by polyimide (PI) tape with a positioned circle pattern (1.5 cm diameter) on its middle, as well as a piece of copper foil as a current collector. Then, 15 μL of each V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene-based slurries were loaded onto the circle pattern as depicted in **Figure 3a**, proceeded with drying in a vacuum oven at 35 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 hours and their pre-electrochemical activation before using as a photocathode in zinc-ion solar battery. An adhesive PI tape with a rectangular shape ($2 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$) served as a substrate on the anode side, with placing a pre-cutted circle shape zinc foil anode (1 μm thickness, 15 mm diameter), and a piece of zinc foil current collector both adhered on a rectangular PI tape (**Figure 3b**). Subsequently, the as-prepared photocathode and anode with a separator (1.8 cm diameter) made of Whatman glass microfiber filter paper, and

50 μL of 2 M $\text{Zn}(\text{TFSI})_2$ aqueous electrolyte were all assembled to make the pouch zinc-ion solar battery cell.

Figure 3. (a, b) Schematic illustration of the processes involved in the step-by-step fabrication of the photocathode and anode pouch zinc-ion solar battery. (c) A digital photo showcasing a pouch zinc-ion solar battery. (d) Schematic depiction the working mechanism of the fabricated zinc-ion solar battery under illumination of the photocathode surface, Zn^{2+} ions diffusion, and charging process. (e) A digital photo displaying operation of the zinc-ion solar battery under illumination by LED solar simulator.

To avoid electrolyte leakage, a piece of parafilm with a ring shape is applied around the separator. **Figure 3c** displays a digital photograph of the pouch zinc-ion solar battery cell. The working mechanism of the fabricated zinc-ion solar battery with light illumination on the photocathode surface, Zn^{2+} ions diffusion, and charging process under LED solar simulator are illustrated in **Figures 3d,e**.

To explore the optoelectronic and electrochemical behaviors of the V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXene-based photocathodes, we established a self-powered photodetector in a beaker cell via a three-electrode system,^[16] as well as a pair of pouch zinc-ion solar battery devices, with both non-electrochemical and electrochemical activated MXene-based photocathodes. The electrochemical activation method was inspired by the method of Liu and co-workers.^[15c] This approach assists in improving the valence of the outermost vanadium in V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ by forming higher oxidation states of vanadium without altering the inner V-C-V structure, providing a unique opportunity to enhance photoactivity, superior electronic and ionic conductivity in solar energy storage systems. To carry out this process, we activated a set of V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXene-based photocathodes using a battery cell setup inside a beaker, where the MXene-based materials served as the cathode, zinc foil as the anode, and 2 M ZnSO_4 as the electrolyte (**Figure S4a**). A charging cut-off voltage of 1.8 V at 2 A g^{-1} was applied to both samples, followed by a 2 hours hold at that voltage. Initial capacities of 1800 and 2350 mAh g^{-1} were achieved for the V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXene-based photocathodes, respectively (**Figures S4b,c**).

The photocurrent responsivities of the non-electrochemical and electrochemical activated V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ samples under three different blue ($\lambda = 435$ nm), green ($\lambda = 533$ nm), and red ($\lambda = 630$ nm) LED lights at intensities of 35 and 75 mW cm^{-2} , with zero applied voltage, are presented in **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**, respectively. Prior to this, we conducted a series of preliminary photosensor tests on the blank PET-coated ITO/Au to confirm that the photocurrents were generated from the MXene-based materials (**Figure S5**). It is distinguished that the absolute photocurrent responses ($|\Delta I| = I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}$) of the electrochemical activated

V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ samples were enhanced by at least twofold under all selected LED lights and intensities. Additionally, the photocurrent responsivity of the $V_2CT_x@S$ was higher than that of pristine V_2CT_x (**Figure 4** and **Figure 5**).

Figure 4. Absolute values of the cyclic photocurrent responses ($|\Delta I| = I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}$) of the non-electrochemical activated (a) V_2CT_x and (b) $V_2CT_x@S$ pouch zinc-ion solar batteries using different LED lights of $\lambda = 435$ nm (35 and 75 $mW\ cm^{-2}$), $\lambda = 533$ nm (75 $mW\ cm^{-2}$), and $\lambda = 630$ nm (75 $mW\ cm^{-2}$), at zero applied voltage. (I_{light} and I_{dark} stand for the currents in dark and illuminated conditions).

Figure 5. Absolute values of the cyclic photocurrent responses ($|\Delta I| = I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}$) of the electrochemically activated (a) V_2CT_x and (b) $V_2CT_x@S$ pouch zinc-ion solar batteries using

different LED lights of $\lambda = 435$ nm (35 and 75 mW cm^{-2}), $\lambda = 533$ nm (75 mW cm^{-2}), and $\lambda = 630$ nm (75 mW cm^{-2}), at zero applied voltage. (I_{light} and I_{dark} stand for the currents in dark and illuminated conditions).

Sample	SSA [m^2/g]	pore volume [cm^3/g]
V_2CT_x	22.400	0.0554
$\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$	49.260	0.0757

Figure 6. (a, b) A comparison between CV characterizations of the V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ zinc-ion solar battery devices with electrochemically activated V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXene-based photocathodes at low and high scan rates of 1 and 10 mV s^{-1} , respectively. (c, d) BET analysis of the synthesized V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ nanopowders.

CV characterizations on the pouch zinc-ion solar battery devices made with non-electrochemically activated (Figure S6) and electrochemically activated (Figures 6a,b) V_2CT_x and $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x@\text{S}$ MXene-based materials indicated significant improvements in electrochemical

behaviors. The CV plots of the electrochemically activated $V_2CT_x@S$, analyzed at both low (1 mV s^{-1}) and high (10 mV s^{-1}) scan rates, were broader than those of pristine V_2CT_x (**Figures 6a,b**). The enhanced photocurrent responsivity and CV performance of the electrochemically activated MXene-based samples are attributed to the formation of higher oxidation states of vanadium. The addition of sulfur element is capable of further tuning the band gap, enhancing light absorption, improving charge carrier dynamics, and introducing active sites for light-induced reactions in $V_2CT_x@S$. Sulfur also can affect redox activity by creating new redox-active sites, improving electrocatalytic performance, which is reflected in the CV profile through increased specific current and altered peak behaviors. Some of these benefits were confirmed by BET characterizations performed on both V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene powders (**Figures 6c,d**). The specific surface area of the synthesized pristine V_2CT_x was $22.400 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$, whilst that of $V_2CT_x@S$ was $49.260 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$. Due to these advantages, $V_2CT_x@S$ was selected for further analysis in the subsequent sections focusing on pouch zinc-ion solar batteries.

To figure out the electrochemical performance of the $V_2CT_x@S$ solar battery, we first carried out CV curves of the device in dark and illuminated conditions recorded at various scan rates ranging from 1 mV s^{-1} to 10 mV s^{-1} (**Figures 7a,b**). An LED light with $\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$ and an intensity of 35 mW cm^{-2} was utilized as the light source for the illumination condition. The CV profiles display four distinct redox peaks, identified as Peak 1, Peak 2, Peak 3, and Peak 4, corresponding to the reversible redox reactions occurring in the electrode material. In the dark condition (**Figure 7a**), as the scan rate increases, the peak currents for all four redox peaks rise proportionally. This behavior indicates a diffusion-controlled redox process, typically seen in battery-type electrodes. Additionally, the shift in peak potentials with increasing scan rates suggests kinetic limitations in the charge transfer processes. Under illumination (**Figure 7b**), the CV profiles maintain a similar shape, however, the peak currents for both cathodic and anodic sweeps are noticeably higher compared to the dark condition at the same scan rates. This suggests that illumination enhances the redox kinetics, possibly by generating photo-induced charge carriers of the photocathode that facilitate faster electron transfer at the electrode interface. The enhanced kinetics under illumination are further supported by the increased peak separation, implying a more reversible redox process.

Figures 7c,d provide a direct comparison of the specific current densities at the lowest (1 mV s^{-1}) and highest (10 mV s^{-1}) applied scan rates, respectively, between the dark and illuminated states. It can be observed that at 1 mV s^{-1} (**Figure 7c**), the illuminated condition displays a valuable increase (26.8%) in both anodic and cathodic currents, emphasizing the influence of light on the electrochemical activity at slower scan rates. At 10 mV s^{-1} (**Figure 7d**), the area

under the CV curve is also larger under illuminated than the dark condition (19.25%), indicating that the photocathode material exhibits enhanced charge storage capabilities when exposed to light.

Figure 7. (a, b) CV curves of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device in dark and illuminated conditions recorded at various scan rates. (c, d) A comparison between CV characterizations of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device under dark and illumination conditions at low and high scan rates of 1 and 10 $mV s^{-1}$. (e, f) The logarithmic relationship between peak current ($\log i$) and scan rate ($\log \nu$) of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device under dark and illumination conditions. (g, h) The charge storage contributions (capacitive and diffusion) of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device under dark and illumination conditions.

This is likely due to improved capacitive behavior, as well as possible contributions from photogenerated carriers that boost the overall redox activity. Additional CV curves showing a comparison between dark and illuminated conditions at scan rates of 2, 3, 5, and 8 $mV s^{-1}$ are provided in **Figure S7**. The capacitive and diffusive energy storage contributions are assessed from these data by the common formula given below, describing the relationship between the peak current (i) and scan rate (ν);^[26]

$$i = i_{\text{diff}} + i_{\text{cap}} = a\nu^b \quad \text{or} \quad \log(i) = \log(a) + b \times \log(\nu)$$

where, i_{diff} , i_{cap} , a and b stand for the diffusion-limited current, capacitive-limited current, and adjustable parameters. The b -values, derived from the slope of the plots provide insight into the nature of the electrochemical charge storage mechanism. A b -value close to 0.5 indicates a diffusion-controlled process, while a b -value close to 1 suggests a capacitive process.^[27] The logarithmic relationship between peak current ($\log i$) and scan rate ($\log \nu$) is plotted in **Figures 7e,f** for dark and illuminated conditions, respectively. In the dark (**Figure 7e**), Peaks 1, 2, and 4 exhibit b -values between 0.70 and 0.74, implying a mixed charge storage mechanism with significant diffusion control. Peak 3, however, shows a higher b -value of 0.87, indicating a more prominent capacitive contribution. Under illumination (**Figure 7f**), the b -values for Peaks 1, 2, and 4 decrease slightly, suggesting a shift towards a more diffusion-controlled process. However, Peak 3 retains a high b -value of 0.87, similar to the dark condition, indicating that

this redox process is largely capacitive and unaffected by light. This behavior may be attributed to specific surface or interface effects that are enhanced by illumination.

Furthermore, the charge storage contributions can be divided into capacitive-controlled (k_1v) and diffusion-controlled ($k_2v^{1/2}$) sections as a function of the voltage which are considered by,^[28]

$$i(V) = k_1v + k_2v^{1/2} \quad \text{or} \quad i(V)v^{-1/2} = k_1v^{1/2} + k_2$$

Thus, we figured out these calculations for each scan rate studied in our CV measurements. **Figures 7g,h** decompose the total charge storage into capacitive- and diffusion-controlled contributions across different scan rates for dark and illuminated conditions, respectively. These values were performed based on the slopes (k_1) and intercepts (k_2) values calculated in dark and illuminated conditions (**Figure S8**). In the dark (**Figure 7g**), the capacitive contribution increases from 48.3% at 1 mV s⁻¹ to 74.7% at 10 mVs⁻¹, highlighting the increasing dominance of surface-controlled processes at higher scan rates. When illuminated (**Figure 7h**), the capacitive contribution is consistently lower at all scan rates compared to the dark condition. It starts at 35.2% at 1 mV s⁻¹ and reaches 63.2% at 10 mV s⁻¹. This reduction suggests that illumination enhances the diffusion-controlled processes, possibly due to improved ionic mobility or deeper penetration of ions into the electrode material under light exposure by photogenerated charges. The results collectively demonstrate that illumination substantially develops the electrochemical behavior of the electrode material. The enhanced redox kinetics and raised specific currents under light exposure suggest that the photocathode material could be harnessed in photo-assisted energy storage systems, where light can directly modulate charge storage processes. The shift in the balance between capacitive- and diffusion-controlled contributions under illumination further supports the hypothesis that light not only boosts electron transfer rates but also modifies ion transport dynamics within the electrodes.

In the next step, we measured GCD curves at different specific currents of 1000, 3000, 5000, 10,000, and 20,000 mA g⁻¹ in dark and illuminated conditions (cut-off voltage range of 0.2–1.5 V). **Figures 8a,b** display the GCD profiles of the V₂CT_x@S solar battery at current densities of 1000 mA g⁻¹ and 20,000 mA g⁻¹, respectively, under illuminated and dark conditions (the other GCD profiles at 3000, 5000, and 10,000 mA g⁻¹ have been included in **Figure S9**). At 1000 mA g⁻¹ (**Figure 8a**), the specific capacity is significantly higher under illumination, reaching nearly 197 mAh g⁻¹, compared to approximately 114 mAh g⁻¹ in the dark (72.80% enhancement,

calculated via $\frac{C_{\text{light}} - C_{\text{dark}}}{C_{\text{dark}}} \times 100\%$, where C_{dark} and C_{light} depict for specific capacitances at the same scan rate in dark and illuminated conditions, respectively).^[10b]

Figure 8. (a, b) GCD curves of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device at two different specific currents of 1000 and $20,000 \text{ mA g}^{-1}$ in dark and illuminated conditions. (c) Specific discharge capacity as a function of the applied current density in dark and illuminated conditions for the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device. (d) The solar battery performance at

varying current densities in dark and illuminated conditions. (e) Nyquist plots and equivalent-circuit diagrams of the zinc-ion solar battery device in (f) dark and (g) illumination conditions.

The enhanced capacity under illumination is likely due to the additional photogenerated charge carriers, which increase the number of active sites for electrochemical reactions. The GCD curves also show that the voltage plateaus are more pronounced under illumination, indicating more stable and efficient energy storage processes. At the higher current density of 20,000 mA g⁻¹ (**Figure 8b**), the specific capacities are reduced for both conditions, but the illuminated state still exhibits a superior performance. The specific capacity under illumination is about 106 mAh g⁻¹, compared to approximately 50 mAh g⁻¹ in the dark. This further supports the hypothesis that illumination improves the charge storage capability, even at higher rates where diffusion limitations are more pronounced.

Figure 8c presents the specific discharge capacity as a function of the applied current density, providing insight into the rate capability of the electrode material. As the current density increases from 1000 mA g⁻¹ to 20,000 mA g⁻¹, the specific capacity decreases for both dark and illuminated conditions. However, the illuminated condition consistently outperforms the dark condition across all current densities, underscoring the positive effect of light on the rate capability. The rate test performance at varying current densities (**Figure 8d**) corresponding to GD curves at different applied specific currents under illuminated and dark conditions reveals that the specific capacity remains relatively stable over multiple cycles. Under illumination, the capacity retention is better, particularly at lower current densities (1000–5000 mA g⁻¹). The specific capacity decreases as the current density increases but relatively stabilizes upon returning to lower current densities specifically under illumination, indicating good reversibility and stability of the electrode material. The qualified cycling performance under illumination suggests that light may mitigate degradation mechanisms typically deteriorated at high current densities, such as electrode polarization or active material dissolution.

Figure 8e and **Figure S10** show the Nyquist plots obtained from electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements under illuminated and dark conditions as well as their fits, respectively. The Nyquist plots consist of (i) an initial combined resistance (R_s) including ionic resistance of the electrolyte, inherent electrode materials resistance, and resistance between the attached electrode and current collector, which all could be appropriated by the real axis semicircle at high frequencies, (ii) a semicircle at high frequencies, attributed to the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), and (iii) a straight line at low frequencies, associated with Warburg impedance, reflecting the diffusion of ions in the electrode.^[29] Under illumination (**Figure 8e**),

the Nyquist plot shows a lower R_s value (4.50Ω) compared to the dark condition with R_s value of 5.85Ω , as well as a smaller semicircle diameter compared to the dark condition, indicating reduced charge transfer resistance. This is likely due to enhanced conductivity and faster electron transfer processes facilitated by photogenerated carriers. The corresponding equivalent circuit models used to fit the EIS data are shown in **Figures 8f,g**, with the fitted parameters confirming a lower R_s (electrolyte resistance) and R_{ct} under illumination. The error values (χ^2) for the fits are 0.23 and 0.66 in dark and illuminated conditions (**Figure S10**), respectively, indicating a good fit for both models. The decrease in R_{ct} under illumination supports the conclusion that light exposure enhances the electrochemical kinetics of the electrode material. Additionally, the Warburg impedance component, representing ion diffusion, shows that the illuminated electrode has better ion transport properties most probably due to the increased conductivity and reduced polarization effects. The results demonstrate that illumination significantly increased specific capacity, improved rate capability, better cycling stability, and reduced charge transfer resistance under light exposure all point to the beneficial effects of photogenerated carriers. These carriers likely increase the number of active sites and reduce polarization, thereby improving both the energy storage capacity and the efficiency of the charge-discharge processes.

The photocharging behavior of the $V_2CT_x@S$ solar battery at 0 A g^{-1} and voltage-floating condition was investigated with the same 435 nm wavelength and intensity of 35 mW cm^{-2} (**Figure S11**). The voltage profile displays a rapid raise in voltage during the photocharging, following a stable voltage during floating. It is seen that the photocharging takes about 1000 seconds to reach 0.7 V . This fast enhancement in voltage shows an effective photo-induced charging in the $V_2CT_x@S$ and an efficient conversion of light energy into electrochemical energy. After that, the voltage reaches a plateau at 0.7 V for additional 1000 seconds. This section expresses that the solar battery system remains charged without external bias or further light-induced charging. The stable voltage stage also demonstrates that the solar battery system has a minimal self-discharge during that period. The voltage floating behavior is crucial in photo-rechargeable energy storage and solar battery systems because it demonstrates the evolution of the device's energy performance following light loading. The prolonged stable condition in voltage stresses the potential of the photocathode and anode materials for long-term energy storage applications where advanced energy storage is essential.

To assess the photocurrent intensity of the $V_2CT_x@S$ solar battery, we examined the photocurrent response under illumination ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, 35 mW cm^{-2}) at three various applied biases of 0 V , 0.2 V , and 1.5 V (**Figures 9a-c**). These three voltage ranges were chosen based

on the applied potential (0.2- 1.5 V) utilized to investigate the electrochemical performance of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery. Photocurrent at 0 V exhibits periodic fluctuations with an absolute peak current of about 22 μA . The periodic nature of the photocurrent implies a steady and repetitive generation of charge carriers under illumination, most likely due to alternating periods of charge generation and recombination. The absence of an external bias indicates that the photogenerated charge carriers drive the photocurrent. Photocurrent at 0.2 V still maintains a periodic pattern, but the amplitude reduces to almost 10 μA . This drop could result from the external bias influencing charge carrier movement, perhaps increasing recombination rates or changing the electric field distribution within the energy storage system. However, the photocurrent amplitude at 1.5 V was raised to 30 μA . The higher applied bias in the last condition presumably allows for faster charge carrier separation and increases the number of carriers contributing to the photocurrent and possibly lowering the recombination rate. **Figure 9d** demonstrates the charging and discharging processes of the $V_2CT_x@S$ solar battery in both illuminated and dark conditions. During the initial photocharging phase, the voltage quickly increases without applying an external current and reaches a peak voltage of 0.7 V (photo cut-off voltage) after 1000 seconds. Consequently, the system enters the photo-discharge phase (at very low rate of 0.02 mA cm⁻²), where the voltage steadily drops while the light source is still on. This indicates a controlled release of stored energy because of slow charge carrier recombination. The voltage drops more quickly in the dark-discharge phase (at very low rate of 0.02 mA cm⁻²), after the light is switched off, indicating a faster release of the remaining stored charge in the absence of light. The sharp reduction during dark-discharge indicates that the photocathode material is strongly reliant on light to sustain charge separation, and without it, the recombination processes dominate, resulting in a quick voltage drop. A comparison between photo-discharge and dark-discharge highlights the importance of light in maintaining the charge-separated state, which is crucial for understanding the material's efficiency and possible uses in light-dependent energy storage devices.

The energy density and power density are critical parameters that determine the efficiency of energy storage devices. **Figures 10a-d** present the energy density, power density of the $V_2C@S$ solar battery under illuminated and dark ($\lambda = 420$ nm, 35 mW cm⁻²) conditions, as well as a comparison of specific capacity, power density, energy density and capacitance enhancement at different specific currents. Under dark conditions, the energy density shows a decreasing trend as the specific current increases (**Figure 10a**). This is expected since higher currents typically result in faster discharging rates, reducing the time available for energy storage and thus lowering energy density. This phenomenon reflects the device's limitations under rapid

discharge conditions. The power density, on the other hand, increases slightly with current, indicating a trade-off between energy density and power density.

Figure 9. Absolute values of the cyclic photocurrent responses ($|\Delta I| = I_{\text{light}} - I_{\text{dark}}$) of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device using LED light of $\lambda = 435$ nm and intensity of 35 mW cm^{-2} at (a) 0 V, (b) 0.2 V, and (c) 1.5 V. (d) Photo-charge, photo-discharge, and dark-discharge behaviors of the zinc-ion solar battery using LED light of $\lambda = 435$ nm and intensity of 35 mW cm^{-2} . (Note: photo-discharge and dark-discharge were performed at very low rate of 0.02 mA cm^{-2}).

The radar plot for the dark condition (**Figure 10b**) shows a moderate balance between specific capacity, energy density, and power density at a lower current density of 1 A g^{-1} . However, as the current increases to 20 A g^{-1} , the capacitance enhancement becomes more pronounced, indicating a shift toward power-centric performance. Under illumination (**Figure 10c**), the energy density is significantly enhanced, especially at lower currents. The shift towards higher energy densities indicates that the light illumination positively impacts the $V_2C@S$ solar battery ability to store energy due to greater photogenerated charges and specific capacitance. Although, the power density under illumination will persist in constant rate of dark conditions. This effect correlates the discharge time value with light intensity. When the light intensity is enhanced, the discharge time value also will grow in the same proportion due to the already enormous

storage charges. Therefore, the power density [$P = (E \times 3600)/t$, $E =$ energy density, and $t =$ discharge time) will remain constant. The radar plot under illuminated conditions (**Figure 10d**) presents a more balanced enhancement across all parameters at both low and high current densities.

Figure 10. (a, c) Calculated energy and power densities of the $V_2CT_x@S$ zinc-ion solar battery device, and (b, d) performance summary of operation modes at different specific currents under dark and illumination ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, 35 mW cm^{-2}), respectively. (e) Long-term cyclic stabilities of the zinc-ion solar battery device after 250 cycles in dark and illumination conditions. (f, g) SEM and EDS images of the $V_2CT_x@S$ photocathodes after dark and illumination cyclic stabilities, respectively.

The specific capacity, energy density, and power density are all considerably higher under illumination, demonstrating the $V_2C@S$ superior performance when exposed to light. This enhancement suggests that light illumination facilitates better charge carrier generation and storage, leading to improved energy storage metrics. The photoconversion efficiency of the $V_2C@S$ solar battery was calculated based on the photo-charging response using the formula: $\eta = \frac{E_{\text{out}}}{E_{\text{in}}} \times 100\% = \frac{E_m \times m}{P_{\text{in}} \times t \times A} \times 100\%$,^[30] where E_m is energy density, m is active photocathode mass (0.0012 mg), P_{in} is illuminated light intensity ($= 35 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$), t is photo-charging time ($= 1000 \text{ s}$, and A is the active surface area under illumination ($= 1.77 \text{ cm}^2$). The calculated photoconversion value is $\approx 2.04\%$. This photoconversion efficiency achieved by the $V_2C@S$ solar battery is notable and significant when compared to the latest distinguished studies (**Table S1**).^[5b, 10b, 12, 16, 26, 30-31]

Figure 10e illustrates the cycling stability of the $V_2C@S$ solar battery device under illuminated and dark conditions over 250 cycles at 4000 mA g^{-1} , focusing on specific discharge capacity and coulombic efficiency. In dark condition, the specific discharge capacity of the solar battery gradually reduces from an initial value of around 97 mAh g^{-1} to 47 mAh g^{-1} after 250 cycles. This decline indicates a moderate cycling stability under dark conditions, which could be attributed to the degradation of active materials or the accumulation of side reactions that impede charge storage. The coulombic efficiency is almost stable in dark condition with a slight drop after around 50 cycles. In contrast, under illumination the $V_2C@S$ solar battery device firstly has high specific discharge capacity of as much as 600 mAh g^{-1} then it reduces after 50 cycles. This higher value in specific discharge capacity is due to the formation of a large amount of photogenerated charge carriers under illumination. In contrast, the coulombic efficiency is low then it gets stable. This phenomenon under illumination could be due to the underlying electrochemical processes of the $V_2C@S$ solar battery at this condition. Generally, in a new battery with fresh electrode materials, active sites for electrochemical reactions are more readily available. This results in high initial specific capacity as the battery can store and deliver a large amount of charge. Over passing time and cycling, possibly a solid electrolyte interface layer

forms on the electrode surfaces especially on the zinc anode. This layer forms due to side reactions between the electrode and the electrolyte. Although the formed layer is essential for stabilizing the battery, its formation consumes active zinc ions, leading to a decrease in the battery's capacity. In addition, repeated cycling can lead to mechanical stress and structural changes in the electrode materials. This can cause loss of active material, cracks in the electrodes, or delamination, all of which contribute to a decrease in specific capacity. Under illumination, especially if the solar battery is exposed to higher temperatures, the electrolyte may degrade faster. This degradation can result in increased resistance and reduced overall efficiency, contributing to capacity fade. In our case, since the established temperature during the test is low due to the low applied light intensity (35 mW cm^{-2}), the electrolyte degradation expected to be nothing. This possibly causes that the specific discharge capacity remains stable after the initial 50 cycles. In the case of a lower value of coulombic efficiency at the beginning of 50 cycles under illumination, a significant portion of the charge is consumed in forming the solid electrolyte interface layer, rather than being stored and released as usable energy. This results in a lower initial coulombic efficiency in that range. Besides, the initial cycles might involve more side reactions such as electrolyte decomposition or unwanted reactions with the electrodes specifically with large amounts of photogenerated charge carriers. This effect also consumes charge without contributing to the energy output, thus lowering the coulombic efficiency. However, once the solid electrolyte interface layer is fully formed and stabilized, fewer side reactions occur, leading to a more stable and higher coulombic efficiency in subsequent cycles. All of these phenomena are typical behaviors observed in many rechargeable batteries, including those used in solar energy storage. Therefore, a proper management of cycling conditions and operating environment can help mitigate these effects and extend the life of the battery. **Figures 10f,g** illustrate SEM and EDS results of the $\text{V}_2\text{C@S}$ photoelectrode surface after stability under dark and illuminated conditions, respectively. It is observed that the morphology and compositions of both photoelectrodes are the same with additional zinc elements belonging to the electrolyte deposited on the photocathodes.

Finally, DFT calculations were performed to investigate the impact of pristine V_2C and functionalized $\text{V}_2\text{C@S}$ on photocathode performance, particularly with their light charging properties. The electronic band structure of both pristine V_2C and functionalized $\text{V}_2\text{C@S}$ exhibits metallic behaviors (**Figures 11a-c**, **Figures S12a-f**, and **Figures S13a-c**). However, a precise analysis of the number and origin of bands crossing the Fermi level reveals significant electronic properties and highlights the role influenced by the terminal groups.

Figure 11. The electronic band structure of (a) V_2C , (b) V_2CO_2 , and (c) V_2CS_2 . PDOS and TDOS of (d) V_2C , (e) V_2CO_2 , and (f) V_2CS_2 . Redistribution of electrons in (g) V_2C , (h) V_2CO_2 , and (i) V_2CS_2 .

A recent study on V_2C material suggests a band gap opening configuration.^[32] Our case (**Figures 11b,c**) shows that the functionalization of V_2C monolayers significantly alters their electronic properties, particularly at the Γ point in the Brillouin zone. **Figure 11b** indicates that oxygen atoms form strong bonds with vanadium, potentially modifying the electronic structure by introducing new states near the Fermi level. The presence of oxygen leads to changes in the band structure, possibly opening a band at the Γ point (0.908 eV) and shifting the positions of the valence and conduction bands. In the case of sulfur, which is less electronegative than oxygen, it tends to donate more electron density to the vanadium atoms, effectively modifying the electronic structure. Thus, sulfur functionalization often results in more significant changes in the band structure at the Γ point (1.23 eV) as shown in **Figure 11c**. This functionalization of

V_2C with sulfur generates the new states within the band gap, tuning the Γ point wider and enhancing the material's optical absorption properties as shown in **Figures S14a,b**.

Additionally, in the case of electronic band structure, V_2CO_2 layers were functionalized with sulfur in three diverse positions of V_2CO_2 S, V_2CO -S1, and V_2CO -S2 monolayers. These configurations tuned the Γ point (0.95 eV) (**Figures S13a-c**). The tuning in the band at the Γ point with a maximum of 1.23 eV for V_2CS_2 could enhance the absorption of visible light, which is essential for solar batteries as shown in **Figures S14a,b**. It displays that the absorption for the V_2CS_2 provides a maximum absorption in the range of 400 nm to 450 nm wavelength.

The projected density of states (PDOS) offers detailed insights into the contributions of different atomic orbitals to the electronic states of a material. **Figures 11d-f** show the PDOS for pristine V_2C , V_2CO_2 , and V_2CS_2 based on the standard electronic structure calculations. In the pristine V_2C , the vanadium 3d-orbitals contribute significantly near the Fermi level. For V_2C functionalized with oxygen, the vanadium 3d-orbitals remain dominant but are shifted to lower energy, which induces tuning of the Γ point band. Additionally, oxygen 2p-orbitals introduce new states below the Fermi level, indicating strong V-O bonding. In the case of sulfur-functionalized V_2C , the vanadium 3d-orbitals continue to be significant near the Fermi level, with potential shifts that broaden Γ point band tuning. The sulfur 3p-orbitals also contribute considerably to the states below and near the Fermi level, suggesting a different bonding nature compared to oxygen.

Further analysis of surface-functionalized V_2CO -S (**Figure S15a**) reveals that sulfur 3p-orbitals remain significant near the Fermi level, inducing narrow Γ point band tuning. In this case, the vanadium 3d-orbitals continue to contribute significant states, with sulfur 3p orbital playing a more prominent role compared to oxygen. In the V_2CO -S1 configuration (**Figure S15b**), vanadium 3d-orbitals remain dominant but are shifted to lower energy levels. The oxygen 2p-orbitals introduce new states below the Fermi level, indicating stronger V-O bonding compared to sulfur. For the V_2CO -S2 configuration (**Figure S15c**), the vanadium 3d-orbitals remain dominant and are also shifted to lower energy levels. In this case, sulfur 3p states and oxygen 2p-orbitals introduce new states below the Fermi level, indicating the p-p hybridization near the Fermi level.

Understanding the interplay between charge density distribution is essential for designing advanced materials with specific electronic properties. The charge density variation for pristine V_2C demonstrates an oscillatory behavior, indicating inherent charge distribution characteristics within the pristine material. This oscillation likely reflects the alternating charge densities associated with the vanadium and carbon atoms in the V_2C lattice. When

functionalized with oxygen, the increased frequency and amplitude of the oscillations suggest a significant perturbation in the charge density, caused by the introduction of oxygen atoms. Due to its higher electronegativity, oxygen attracts electron density from the surrounding vanadium and carbon atoms, leading to pronounced regions of electron depletion and accumulation. In contrast, the charge difference upon sulfur functionalization reveals oscillations whose amplitude can be compared with the oxygen-functionalized plot to understand the relative impact of sulfur. **Figures 11g-i** and **Figures S1a-c** illustrate the redistribution of electrons at the surface, showing electron depletion below the surface of V_2C and increased electron accumulation near the surface layer when sulfur is introduced.^[33] This pattern confirms a built-in electric field direction from the surface to the underlying layers of the material. In energy storage systems, controlling charge density distribution by functionalization can enhance the performance by improving electron transfer efficiency.

4. Conclusions

This study introduces a revolutionary exploration of the progress of single-architecture pouch zinc-ion solar batteries using $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene nanocomposites as an efficient photocathode for such modern energy storage devices. Initially, photoactivity performances of the pristine V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ nanocomposites were assessed in two non-electrochemical and electrochemical activated samples. It was observed that by the initial electrochemical charging activation, the photoactivity of the $V_2CT_x@S$ photocathode was enhanced significantly. The reason for this impact was the formation of vanadium oxide at the nanoscale on the conductive V_2CT_x MXene surface, along with the existence of sulfur element without altering the intrinsic MXene nanolayered structure. Next, the focus shifted to evaluating the $V_2CT_x@S$ nanocomposite in a pouch zinc-ion solar battery. The investigation included exposing a light intensity of 35 mW cm^{-2} with $\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$. The results showed a capacitance enhancement of 72.8% at 1 A g^{-1} and a specific capacity of 197 mAh g^{-1} under illumination, compared to its initial 114 mAh g^{-1} in dark conditions. Moreover, the study achieved a peak photo-charging voltage output of 700 mV and a promising energy density of 255 Wh kg^{-1} at 1 A g^{-1} when exposed to light. Besides, the pouch zinc-ion solar battery achieved a photoconversion efficiency of approximately 2.04%. The combination of experimental findings and DFT investigations reveal that sulfur modification, nanoscale vanadium oxide formation, and V-C-V nanolayered structure of the V_2CT_x MXene enhance the electronic properties and ability to absorb light compared to pristine V_2CT_x MXene. This research foresees the enormous possibilities of 2D MXene nanomaterials in creating a strong foundation for innovative off-grid

energy storage devices. Also, it suggests the potential for developing other MXene-based nanostructures with appropriate surface chemistry modifications for future flexible solar energy storage devices. This expectation stems from the efficient mass production capability of 2D MXenes and their exceptional intrinsic properties. The attributes that could allow for the creation of a straightforward and effective device design when compared to the current options with built-in energy harvesting and electrochemical energy storage modules.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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The photoactivity of dual-functional cathodes based on MXene materials is significant in single-architecture zinc-ion solar batteries. The recently developed solar energy storage systems combine photovoltaic and energy storage functions in only one package, aiming to enhance energy storage and minimize energy transmission losses among individual modules. This also makes the overall setup lighter and decreases the size of the package.

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Photoactivity Enhancement by Electrochemical Activation of Bifunctional $V_2C@S$ MXene: Desirable Approach in Single-architecture High-rate Zinc-ion Solar Batteries

Supporting Information

Photoactivity Enhancement by Electrochemical Activation of Bifunctional $V_2C@S$ MXene: Desirable Approach in Single-architecture High-rate Zinc-ion Solar Batteries

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Figure S1. (a, b) Top and side views of the optimized geometries for V_2C monolayer. Side view of the most stable structure for (c) V_2CO_2 , (d) V_2CS_2 , (e) V_2CO_2S , (f) V_2CO-S1 , and (g) V_2CO-S_2 monolayer.

Figure S2. SEM and EDS images of the synthesized V_2CT_x nanopowder.

Figure S3. (a, d) 2D and (b, e) 3D topographical mapping catalytic activities of drop-casted V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene-based slurries, along with the tip current (i_{norm}) and roughness (z) values of the (c) V_2CT_x and (d) $V_2CT_x@S$ corresponding to the 2D topographical results.

Figure S4. (a) A schematic illustrations of electrochemical activation of the MXene-based photocathode in a beaker. (b, c) Initial specific capacities for the V_2CT_x and $V_2CT_x@S$ MXene-based photocathodes, respectively, during their electrochemical charging activation with 1.8 cut-off voltage.

Figure S5. The photocurrent activity of the blank ITO-coated Au substrate.

Figure S6. CV curves of the non-electrochemically activated (a,b) V₂CT_x, and (c, d) V₂CT_x@S MXene-based photocathodes at 0.5 and 10 mV s⁻¹.

Figure S7. Comparative CV curves at different scan rates of 2, 3, 5, and 8 mV s⁻¹ in dark and 35 mW cm⁻² illumination with $\lambda = 435$ nm for the V₂CT_x@S pouch zinc-ion solar battery.

Figure S8. The slopes (k_1) and intercepts (k_2) values of the $V_2CT_x@S$ pouch zinc-ion solar battery calculated in (a) dark and (b) illuminated conditions.

Figure S9. Comparative CD curves at different specific currents of 3000, 5000, and 10000 mA g⁻¹ in dark and 35 mW cm⁻² illumination with $\lambda= 435$ nm for the $V_2CT_x@S$ pouch zinc-ion solar battery.

Figure S10. The fitted EIS of the $V_2CT_x@S$ pouch zinc-ion solar battery in both dark and illumination conditions ($\lambda = 435$ nm, intensity of 35 mW cm^{-2}) with their errors.

Figure S11. Voltage floating test under continuous light ($\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}, 35 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$) illumination at 0 A g^{-1} on the $\text{V}_2\text{CT}_x\text{@S}$ pouch zinc-ion solar battery.

Figure S12. Band structures of (a) V_2C , (b) V_2CO_2 , (c) V_2CS_2 , (d) V_2CO_2 -S, (e) V_2CO -S1, and (f) V_2CO -S2 monolayers.

Figure S13. Band structure of (a) $\text{V}_2\text{CO}_2\text{-S}$, (b) $\text{V}_2\text{CO-S1}$, and (c) $\text{V}_2\text{CO-S2}$ monolayers.

Figure S14. Optical absorption of (a) V_2C , V_2CO_2 and V_2CS_2 monolayers, and (b) $\text{V}_2\text{CO}_2\text{-S}$, $\text{V}_2\text{CO-S1}$ and $\text{V}_2\text{CO-S2}$ monolayers.

Figure S15. Projected and Total density of states of (a) V_2CO_2 -S, (b) V_2CO -S1, and (c) V_2CO -S2 monolayers.

Figure S16. Charge density redistribution of (a) V_2C , (b) V_2CO_2 , and (c) V_2CS_2 monolayers.

Table S1. Comparing the features and efficiencies of some recent reported photo-rechargeable single architecture energy storage devices with the findings of this research work.

Photo-enhanced energy storage system	Electrolyte	Architecture	Illumination	Specific Capacitance	Energy- and Power-density	Voltage response	Photo enhancement capacity	Photo-charge conversion efficiency	Ref
Carbon dots modified Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x -based fibrous supercapacitor	1M H ₂ SO ₄	Single	400 nm ≤ λ ≤ 800 nm, intensity ~ 150 mW cm ⁻²	630 F g ⁻¹ @ 10 A cm ⁻³	0.01872 Wh cm ⁻³ and 8.382 W cm ⁻³	400 mV	35.9%	-	[31]
Nickel-cobalt-deposited tungsten-doped TiO ₂ nanotube supercapacitor	3 M KOH	Single	Visible, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	0.0752 F cm ⁻² @ 0.04 mA cm ⁻²	33.93 × 10 ⁻³ Wh cm ⁻² and 7.54 × 10 ⁻³ W cm ⁻² @ 0.04 mA cm ⁻²	450 mV	46%	-	[31b]
BiVO ₄ -V ₂ O ₅ @titania nanotubes supercapacitor	3M KCl	Single	Visible, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	0.288 F cm ⁻² @ 0.12 mA cm ⁻²	0.04 Wh cm ⁻² and 24 × 10 ⁻⁵ W cm ⁻² @ 0.23 mA cm ⁻²	150 mV	65%	-	[31c]
Cu foam-supported CuO _x @NiCuO _x	2M KOH	Single	Perfect Light PLS-SXE300, intensity 1.76 W	2.64 F cm ⁻²	~ 8 Wh m ⁻² and ~ 80 W m ⁻²	600 mV	44%	-	[31d]
Sulfur-, tungsten-doped TiO ₂ nanotube supercapacitor	0.5 M H ₂ S O ₄	Single	λ = 533 nm, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	0.031 F cm ⁻² @ 0.23 mA cm ⁻²	6.21 Wh cm ⁻² And 399 W cm ⁻² @ 0.23 mA cm ⁻²	400 mV	-	-	[31e]
Zinc-ion capacitor using 2D g-C ₃ N ₄	2M ZnSO ₄	Single	λ = 420 nm, intensity ~ 50 mW cm ⁻²	11.377 F g ⁻¹ @ 5 mA g ⁻¹	~ 0.668 Wh kg ⁻¹ and ~ 1.625 W kg ⁻¹ @ 5 mA g ⁻¹	850 mV	82%	0.01%	[30]
ITO/PET Supercapacitor	1 M LiPF ₆ salt in ethylene carbonate and diethyl	Single	Intensity 100 mW cm ⁻²	0.127 Ah g ⁻¹ (after 1000 cycles) 1 A g ⁻¹	40 Wh kg ⁻¹ and 2000 W kg ⁻¹	3 V	8.41%	-	[31f]

	carbonate (1:1; v/v)								
Zinc-ion capacitor using Ag@V ₂ O ₅ -activated carbon	3 M Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	Single	$\lambda = 455$ nm, intensity ~ 12 mW cm ⁻²	138 F g ⁻¹	~ 53.13 Wh kg ⁻¹ and ~ 36.74 W kg ⁻¹	500 mV	63%	0.05%	[31g]
Mg-ion capacitor using VO ₂	1 M Mg(NO ₃) ₂	Single	$\lambda = 455$ nm, intensity ~ 12 mW cm ⁻²	63.80 F g ⁻¹ @ 0.65 A g ⁻¹	~ 0.0205 Ah kg ⁻¹	70 mV	56%	-	[31h]
Zinc-ion capacitor using Germanane	2M ZnSO ₄	Single	$\lambda = 435$ nm, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	4 F g ⁻¹ @ 5 mA g ⁻¹	0.360 Wh kg ⁻¹ and ~ 2 W kg ⁻¹ @ 5 mA g ⁻¹	970 mV	52%	-	[10b]
Zinc-ion capacitor using Cyanoethyl-Germanane	2M ZnSO ₄	Single	$\lambda = 435$ nm, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	6.167 F g ⁻¹ @ 5 mA g ⁻¹	0.548 Wh kg ⁻¹ and ~ 3.091 W kg ⁻¹ @ 5 mA g ⁻¹	1000 mV	26%	-	[10b]
Zinc-ion capacitor using Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x MXene	2M ZnSO ₄	Single	$\lambda = 420$ nm, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	84 F g ⁻¹ @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	9.4 Wh kg ⁻¹ and ~ 90 W kg ⁻¹ @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	960 mV	$\sim 30\%$	0.01%	[5b]
Zinc-ion capacitor using Te/Ti ₃ C ₂ T _x MXene	2M ZnSO ₄	Single	$\lambda = 420$ nm, intensity ~ 100 mW cm ⁻²	73 F g ⁻¹ @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	8.2 Wh kg ⁻¹ and ~ 90 W kg ⁻¹ @ 0.2 A g ⁻¹	960 mV	50%	0.07%	[5b]
Zinc-ion capacitor using Nb ₂ CT _x MXene	2M ZnSO ₄	Single	$\lambda = 435$ nm, intensity ~ 50 mW cm ⁻²	27 F g ⁻¹ @ 10 mA g ⁻¹	2.4 Wh kg ⁻¹ and 40 W kg ⁻¹ @ 30 mA g ⁻¹	1000 mV	60%		[16]
Photo-rechargeable zinc ion battery using rGO/VO ₂ /Ag	3 M Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	Single	$\lambda = 455$ nm, intensity ~ 12 mW cm ⁻²	370 mA h g ⁻¹ @ 50 mA g ⁻¹	-	890 mV	95%	1.2%	[12b]
Photo-rechargeable zinc ion battery using MoS ₂ -ZnO	3 M Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	Single	$\lambda = 455$ nm, intensity ~ 12 mW cm ⁻²	340 mA h g ⁻¹ @ 100 mA g ⁻¹	-	940 mV	38.8%	1.8%	[26]

Photo-rechargeable zinc-ion battery using VO ₂	3 M Zn(CF ₃ SO ₃) ₂	Single	$\lambda = 455 \text{ nm}$, intensity $\sim 100 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$	315 mA h g ⁻¹ @ 200 mA g ⁻¹	-	890 mV	11.7%	0.18%	[12a]
V ₂ CT _x @S Zinc ion solar battery	2 M Zn(TFSI) ₂	Single	$\lambda = 435 \text{ nm}$, intensity $\sim 35 \text{ mW cm}^{-2}$	197 mA h g ⁻¹ @ 1000 mA g ⁻¹	255 Wh kg ⁻¹ and 1.3 W kg ⁻¹ @ 1000 mA g ⁻¹	700 mV	72.8%	2.04%	This work